

1 **Title:** Methodological limitations in assessing influenza vaccine effectiveness in school
2 children: A call for rigorous clinical epidemiology

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20 **To the Editor,**

21 We read with interest the article by Kajiume et al. reporting a 10-year investigation of
22 influenza vaccine effectiveness in elementary and middle schools. 1) While the
23 longitudinal data on immunization rates among Japanese school children offer useful
24 descriptive context, we have serious concerns about the study's methodology and the
25 authors' conclusion that infant influenza vaccination increases the subsequent risk of
26 influenza infection through "original antigenic sin." The study design has critical flaws
27 that preclude any such causal inference.

28 **Outcome misclassification.**

29 The study relies entirely on self-reported questionnaires for influenza diagnosis, with no
30 laboratory confirmation by rapid antigen testing or PCR. Without virological verification,
31 influenza cannot be distinguished from other respiratory illnesses, rendering non-
32 specific misclassification unavoidable. The current methodological standard for VE
33 research—the test-negative case-control (TNCC) design—requires precisely this
34 confirmatory step to define cases. In the absence of such confirmation, the outcome
35 variable itself is undefined, and any quantitative estimation of VE is therefore
36 methodologically invalid, not merely imprecise. 2)

37 **Unmeasured confounding.**

38 The analysis is limited to univariate chi-square tests, with no adjustment for age, sex,
39 comorbidities, sibship, or socioeconomic status. This is insufficient for any claim of
40 causal directionality.

41 **Health-seeking behavior bias.**

42 Families adhering to annual vaccination schedules generally have higher health literacy
43 and are more likely to seek evaluation even for mild illness; unvaccinated individuals are
44 more likely to avoid clinical contact. The authors assert that Japan's universal
45 healthcare system and school policies minimize this bias, but this claim is
46 unsubstantiated. The net effect is systematic overestimation of incidence in the
47 vaccinated group. 3)

48 **Recall bias.**

49 Although the study retrospectively assesses past exposures in a manner analogous to a
50 case-control design, no adjustment is made for recall bias. Eliciting "vaccination history
51 since infancy" via a cross-sectional questionnaire administered a decade later, without
52 validation against medical records, fundamentally compromises exposure
53 ascertainment.3)

54 **Selection bias from exclusion of partial vaccinees.**

55 Third, excluding partially vaccinated participants (16.08% of the cohort) introduces
56 significant selection bias. A valid methodological justification is strictly required when
57 excluding such a substantial portion of the study population. However, the authors fail to
58 provide any clear rationale for this decision. Without transparency, one cannot dismiss
59 the serious concern that this data selection was intentionally made to steer the results in
60 a direction favorable to the authors' narrative.

61 **Unsupported mechanistic inference.**

62 Finally, concluding that past vaccination increases influenza morbidity, despite
63 completely failing to adjust for biases and confounding factors, is highly inappropriate.

64 Rather than attributing their findings to complex immunological phenomena like "original
65 antigenic sin," the authors should have critically evaluated these fundamental
66 methodological flaws—specifically, recall bias and over-reporting bias by health-
67 conscious individuals—in their limitations section. Constructing an argument driven by a
68 preconceived conclusion, rather than objective epidemiological data, is scientifically
69 untenable.

70 In conclusion, causal inferences regarding the adverse effects of infant vaccination
71 cannot be derived from this study. Its scientific contribution should be strictly confined to
72 describing the current landscape of pediatric influenza vaccination in Japan.

73 Investigating the long-term immunological consequences and true VE will require
74 adequately powered prospective cohort studies with virological confirmation and
75 rigorous confounder adjustment.

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88 **Declarations**

89 • **Ethics approval and consent to participate:** Not applicable.

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